

Approaches to the Truth in Analytical Chemistry : The Accurate Result

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To achieve good analytical accuracy requires the development of methodology of high precision of measurement which in turn, depends on the concentration of the analyte being determined. The analytical signals should be well above the limit of detection (LOD) and measured above the limit of quantitation (LOQ) of the method. These two parameters are related to the magnitude and reproducibility of the blank. The method so evolved should be rugged. Sources of analytical biases have been pointed out. The presence of biases in the analytical data can be identified by two-sample plots as well as other approaches. These aspects are discussed with examples.

TEXT Books on Analytical Chemistry define 'analytical accuracy' as a measure of the agreement of the experimental results with the True value, or the Most-probable value for the content of the analyte in a sample¹⁻³. When an analytical scientist analyses a sample, he does not know the true content of the analyte, that is why he does the analysis. So, it is easy to have analytical accuracy defined as above, but it is not easily assessed. Since the road towards the truth in analytical chemistry (the accurate result) is not easy to negotiate, nor well laid out, an attempt has been made in this article to identify important milestones on the proper road.

Discussion

Compared to the intangible definition of accuracy given above, Morrison and Skogerboe⁴ have a better definition: "Precision defines the accuracy that can be achieved in the absence of systematic errors". The emphasis is on the precision of analytical measurements and the identification of the sources and the magnitudes of the systematic errors in the methodology. This has been referred to in the literature as the 'eye of the bull' concept and pictorially described by Cali and Reed⁵ (Fig. 1). It is clear that to have good analytical accuracy the measurement process should have high precision. Aspects of analytical methodology which can help improve the precision of measurements, and the identification of the sources of errors, as well as their influence on accuracy, will be discussed below.

Improvement of the precision of analysis :

Selection of the analytical methodology : The importance of selection of analytical technique and the related methodology can be shown from the example of determination of trace elements in natural rocks. The run-of-the mill precision of four

Fig. 1. Precision and accuracy.

methods⁶ used for this analysis *viz.* atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), optical emission spectroscopy (OES) and neutron activation analysis (NAA) for some selected elements is depicted in Figs. 2 and 3. In the preparation of

these plots the primary data of the well known U.S. Geological Standards (USGS)⁷ have been used. The data were first grouped technique-wise, the obvious outliers rejected and the mean and standard deviation (s.d.-1) of the results computed. Using the mean \pm 1 s.d.-1 values for the boundaries, the selected data used for the 'preferred mean' and a standard deviation (s.d.-2) of these selected data. The relative standard deviations (RSD) so computed are then plotted against the concentrations. The criterion of choosing 1 s.d. limits for the rejection of the primary data is arbitrary and cannot be justified by accepted statistical methods which usually assume a 'normally distributed set of primary data'; which

they often are not. One justification for such arbitrary selection is that comparable approaches have been used earlier by other compilers^{8,9}. Further, it has the advantage that the very high and low values by the respective techniques are pruned out of the primary data sets, which often have different degrees of skewness, so that the comparison of the performance of techniques is fair. The elements selected for the plots are those which are analysed with different degrees of confidence by the techniques—some, good; some, not so good. It is seen that there is rapid increase in the 'imprecision' of the results as the analyte concentrations are below 50 ppm. On the other hand the precision of

Fig. 2. Spread of analytical data.

Fig. 3. Precision in the geological trace analysis by NAA: Samples: UGS (Stds.): GSP-1, AGV-1, W-1, DTS-1, BCR-1; \bar{x}_p values: data from Ref. 7; element, symbol, range (ppm): Cr (11) x (5) 7-3900; Ce (12), † (3), 48-150; Co (10), O (6), 5-130; Sb (9), □ (6), 0.06-3; U (10), ● (5), 0.04-2; Th (11), Δ (6), 0.01-100.

the NAA data do not change so rapidly till the concentrations are much lower because of the intrinsic capability of the technique to determine lower concentrations. The overall performance of the techniques, as reflected by these figures in intercomparison work, is poorer than their intrinsic precision, as normally seen in the intra-laboratory data. Therefore, there must be differences in the details of the analytical methodology practiced by the different laboratories which affect the data.

The importance of analytical methodology (as different from technique) is also clear from the work on the mercury content of the IAEA reference sample H-4 (Ref. 10). The two techniques used are NAA and AAS. The interference-free limit of detection for NAA is 10^{-3} ng, while that of the cold vapour atomic absorption is 0.1 ng (for 1% absorbance). The more coherent data in this work is obtained by the radiochemical NAA and also by the cold vapour atomic absorption method. The other laboratories who participated and who used INAA and other options of AAS have reported only their detection limits. Apparently, the instrumental option of NAA with high practical limits is not an appropriate method for this analysis in this matrix at this level of concentration. Unlike the above clear example there are many other instances where it is not clear whether the reported data have been at around the limits of the method. At an advisory meeting¹¹ of the IAEA, the experts examined the approaches involving NAA, AAS, ICP-AES, chemical (also ASV, SSMS and PIXE) to identify the most versatile one useful for the analysis of 28 trace elements in four biological samples ranging from serum to a vegetable standard. They opined that if data of 10% uncertainty is required then NAA and AAS with separation steps, *viz.* RNAA, or FAAS with pre-separation will be the most appropriate ones. Two useful criteria in the selection of methodology are (i) whether the limit of quantitation (LOQ) of

the method is lower than the concentration at which the analysis is required and (ii) the ruggedness of the methodology. These are discussed in some detail below.

LOD and LOQ of methods: The achievable precision of analytical measurements is related to the detection capability of methods, because the 'imprecision of the data' increases as the analyte concentration approaches the instrumental limits of detection of the method (IDL). This is brought out by the well known studies on absorption spectrometric measurements. This analytical technique is referred to because the largest number of publications in the field of Analytical Chemistry in this journal are by this technique. The 'theoretical error curve' dealing with the 'random errors' of absorption measurements increases exponentially with decrease in the measured absorbance¹², and hence the concentration of the analyte; that is to say, when one approaches the limit of detection (erroneously often referred to as sensitivity; sensitivity is measured by the slope of the linear calibration curve). Hence, the great interest in devising new colour systems of higher molar absorptivity so that one can get a higher absorbance for the same analyte concentration; as also the development of preconcentration methods, *e.g.* extractive spectrophotometry.

As different from the IDL, the IUPAC has defined the limit of detection of method as follows. "The limit of detection, LOD, expressed as the concentration, (C_L) or the quantity, (q_L) is derived from the smallest measure X_L , that can be detected with reasonable certainty for a given analytical procedure"¹³. This definition has been accepted by the American Chemical Society (ACS) in 1980 and 1983 (Refs. 14,15). However, the expression, 'that can be detected with reasonable certainty', has been clarified by the ACS as 'that can be determined to be statistically different from a blank value'. This

definition leads to the following expression,

$$X_L = \bar{X}_{bl} + k s_{bl}$$

where, \bar{X}_{bl} is the average of independent measures of blanks ($n \sim 20$) with the corresponding standard deviation, s_{bl} . With the magnitude of k fixed at 3, one has the assurance that the uncertainty that the measured signal (X_L) is not a measure of blank is only 0.13%, or there is a 99.86% confidence that the measured signal X_L , at $(\bar{X}_{bl} + 3s_{bl})$ is a true signal and not a blank measure. While this definition provides a statistically defined smallest signal which is not a blank signal, quantitation of concentrations on such signals are expected to have high imprecision. Hence, the American Chemical Society has recommended that quantitation should be made only on signals which are higher by $10s_{bl}$ above \bar{X}_{bl} . Thus the limit of quantitation LOQ is

$$X_{LO} = \bar{X}_{bl} + 10s_{bl}$$

The concepts LOD and LOQ are shown in Fig. 4. It is to be pointed out that LOD is conceptually different from the IDL which refers to the smallest signal which an instrument can detect above the background noise, *i.e.* the smallest signal which can be detected just above 3 times the standard deviation of the average noise¹⁵.

It is clear from the above discussion that there is nothing like LOD of techniques. Certain techniques can have intrinsic interference-free LODs computed from measurements made at optimised predetermined conditions of experiments, which are, at best, useful guidelines. For example, the 'sensitivity limits' reported in the literature for neutron activation analysis^{16,17}, are computed for pure elements, irradiated at predetermined period in a specified flux of neutrons and the induced activity having been measured under specified conditions. The problems of computing LOD for spectrochemical methods using calibration curves have been discussed by Young and Winefordner¹⁸.

The definition of IUPAC and American Chemical Society focuses the importance of the magnitude and reproducibility of blank which influence the LOD and LOQ of the methodology and not the technique *per se*, as pointed out earlier.

Ruggedness of analytical methods: Lack of consistency of results in quality control work could often be traced to the lack of ruggedness of the analytical methods in use. An analytical procedure is rugged¹⁹ if the precision of the results is not influenced by small departures from the described procedure. The departures are reasonably small and are as expected when the procedure is followed by different scientists in the participating laboratories. The pioneering work on this subject by Youden¹⁹ continues to be a classic. To establish the ruggedness of a method it may be necessary to examine many experimental parameters which can be time consuming. Economy of efforts can be made by multifactorial experiments²⁰.

This concept was demonstrated by this author in a recent publication²¹ dealing with the development of a high precision spectrophotometric method for the vexatious analytical problem of determination of silica in rocks. In this study, 14 experimental parameters were examined in groups of seven in two sets of each eight experiments which has shown that a relative standard deviation of 0.35% is achievable in the determination of SiO_2 in the range of concentration 45-75%, provided that the time-lag between the development of β -heteropolysilicomolybdate colour and its absorbance measurement is within 10-12 min. While this example is in the area of a major element analysis, the concept can also be adopted for the development of rugged trace element methods.

Emphasis so far has been on the approaches needed to improve the precision of the final determination. To achieve accuracy what is needed is

Fig. 4. Relationship of LOD and LOQ to signal strength (from Ref. 15).

to identify the sources of systematic errors and their avoidance.

Sources of biases :

Laboratory, man and practices : Many of the systematic errors in analyses, particularly at trace concentrations, can be traced to the stage of sample pretreatment (Fig. 5)²². In this figure, the methods of determination are arranged in such a way that as one goes down the line there is an increase of the number of steps of sample pre-treatment, as normally required, to get adequate selectivity, or for improving the detection limits. It does not mean that the methods which need many such steps are not dependable ; nor the converse, but it does mean that additional efforts are needed to avoid systematic errors in such methods.

Fig. 5. Analytical methodology.

At the pre-treatment stage, the sample can be contaminated by the container, materials used for sub-sampling (cutting tools syringes etc.), the laboratory environment or the chemical reagents. It is also possible that the analyte could be lost to the container (adsorption losses to the container), during the steps of separation or preconcentration. These aspects have been discussed in the literature²³⁻²⁵. A few interesting examples, however, are given below to show how the laboratory, man and practices could be the sources of biases.

Laboratory : Murphy²⁶ has given a comparison of particulate density in the air of ordinary laboratory, clean room and a class '100' hood. For example, the concentration of iron in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ decreases from 0.2 to 0.0009 when one changes from an ordinary laboratory to a clean hood. The corresponding reduction in the case of lead is from 0.4 to 0.0003 ; while cadmium decreases by a factor of 10. These values are valid for a US laboratory. The values for normal Indian Laboratory could be higher by one or two orders of magnitude.

Man : The example is by Berman²⁶ which focuses the lead contamination present on the

person of the analyst. The amount of lead found on the fingers of technicians who already had washed their hands ranged from 0.16 to about 0.4 μg .

Practices : One bad practice by some analysts is to eject the last drop in pipettes used for the transfer of standard solutions. After washing the pipette with deionised water the last drops are removed by jerking the pipettes. At this stage the damage is not high. However, as a bad practice it is followed at the next stage when the pipette, after rinsing with the standard solution is also jerked to remove the last drop on to the floor. This practice leads to the build-up of contamination of the laboratory, usually by the analyte present at high levels of concentrations in standard solutions. The residues from these drops finally get attached to the particles in the laboratory, back again to the samples.

The use of tissue papers to wipe the pipettes, for the removal of the last drops from the pipette, is a common practice. While studying the 'process blank' in the analysis of blood samples for lead in our laboratory about 200 mg of tissue paper was left deliberately in the electrolysis cell of an ASV equipment. In the absence of the paper the process blank was between 4-6 ppb but in the presence of the tissue paper the value was 18 ppb. This amounts to the addition of about 140 ng of lead to a 10 ml solution by leaching from the paper²⁷.

Process blanks : All analytical measurements are corrected for blanks. However, at times the details are overlooked. For example, to assess the contribution to the analytical signal from the acids used for the decomposition of samples it is not uncommon to analyse a volume of the acid (with appropriate dilution) and use the measured signal for correction. This does not represent the process blank needed for a proper blank correction. In the common practice of decomposition of the sample in a covered beaker with the addition of several instalments of the acids, the volatile elements Hg, Se and As are lost during the decomposition ; while the non-volatiles, like Cu, Pb and Cd get concentrated compared to the concentration of the acid ; hence, the need for closed system decomposition, the simplest being the Bethge's apparatus²⁸ (Fig. 6).

Some other sources : It is taken for granted that calibrated volumetric ware are used and there are no personal biases, either in the measurement or in the recording of the data. It is interesting that the tare weights entered in the laboratory note books do not often end in numbers like 1, 3, 7 and 9, an unlikely event on a statistical basis. However, the errors arising from the personal preferences of numbers in this case do not contribute much to the total errors of analysis ; but is a pointer.

The biases arising from wrong calculations are not uncommon. But if they are identified later

Fig. 6. Modified Bethge apparatus for the wet decomposition of organic matter.

they are not usually reported. A rare example is an errata in a journal dealing with the analysis of uranium⁸⁹. The author informed the readers that a conversion factor from U_3O_8 to U was not taken into account, hence the 17% bias in his data.

Change in the composition of dilute standards on long storage is common, hence the slope of calibration curve, has to be checked periodically.

Approaches to identify the biases in the final analytical data :

Use of reference samples : In order to assess the biases of the method, one of the requirements is to have reference samples of known contents. These could be in-house standards, or Internationally recognised standards. The most important of these standards are the 'Standard Reference Materials' from the National Bureau of Standards⁹⁰, U.S.A. 'SRMs are defined as being well characterised and certified materials produced in quantity to improve measurement science. They are prepared and used for three main purposes, (i) to help develop accurate methods of analysis (Reference Methods), (ii) to calibrate measurement systems used to (a) facilitate the exchange of goods, (b) institute quality control etc., and (iii) to assure the long term adequacy and integrity of quality control processes. The SRMs are characterised mostly by the intensive efforts of the National Bureau of Standards using 'definitive' or

'reference methods' of analysis which lead to coherent data before the material is certified⁹⁰.

The other International Standards are evolved from international inter-comparison efforts and they evolve in several stages. The homogeneous sample, prepared by one organisation is distributed to other scientists who volunteer to participate in the characterisation of this material. At this stage it is referred to as an 'intercomparison sample'. The results from these laboratories are then examined by the scientist responsible for the preparation and certification. The primary data using different methods usually exhibit a wide range. Methods of examination of such data for the outliers and the skewness are discussed in the literature. The selected data are evaluated to derive the reference values which are designated as 'indicative average, usable value, consensus or recommended value'⁹¹. It is necessary to follow the methodology used for the derivation of such values and the criteria adopted for such expressions as given above while specifying the quality of the reference values^{91,92}. Further, the status of the 'quality' of the value changes with further re-evaluation on the basis of fresh data which also affect the magnitudes of the recommended values⁹¹. Hence in reporting of analytical results using reference samples as standards, the values for the reference sample should also be included so that the results could be normalised if a more dependable value for the reference sample is available.

Two sample plots : One of the very practical methods of identification of biased results was suggested by Youden⁹³. This method is based on the following. (i) No two individual scientists, whether they follow the same methodology or different ones, in their attempt to establish the true content of the analyte in the sample, have the same systematic error. (ii) It is generally accepted that the errors of analysis are (a) matrix dependent and (b) concentration related, i.e. the errors increase with diminishing content.

To identify the biases in the results of different laboratories, two samples of comparable nature and having similar concentrations are analysed simultaneously by the participating laboratories. A plot of the results of one sample vs the other indicates the relative positions of the laboratories in this plot. Invariably the net distribution is elliptical and not circular as expected in the absence of biases. This arises from the fact that each laboratory has nearly the same bias for the two sample values; the result is a point which is close to a 45° line with the axes. On an examination of such data from similar pairs of samples, if a particular laboratory shows a consistent pattern of bias, the laboratory is advised to check its methodology. The work of Youden was applied by this author⁸⁴ to examine the trace element data of geological standards. Use of such plots allows the rejection of the highly biased data and the

derivation of an unbiased value for such samples. The usefulness of this approach is demonstrated in this paper for which one of the trace constituents, viz. cobalt, in the two USGS standards, G-2 and GSP-1 of comparable chemical composition, is taken as an example. The primary data as of 1982 are available from the publication of Gladney and Burns⁵⁵. There are 80 identifiable pairs of data ; 26 by OES, 26 by NAA, 10 by XRF, and 18 by AAS, each of the pair of data having been reported by the same author by the same method. Sixty of these pairs of data are plotted in Fig. 7. The rest of the 20 pairs cover the range of 3.5-5.5 for G-2 and 5-8 ppm for GSP-1. Since the points corresponding to these data will cluster around the centre of the plot, they are excluded to maintain the clarity of the figure.

Fig. 7. Distribution of cobalt values : (○) OES, (△) AAS, (x) XRF and (●) NAA.

The presence of biases in the data sets is clear as many points are located along the 45° line through the centre, defined in this case, by the geometric means of the primary data of the respective sample. Since the least biased data for GSP-1 are in the range of 5-9 and for G-2 in the range of 3.5-7.2 ppm, all the primary data, independent of the method, which fall within these ranges are averaged to get the unbiased means which are 6.9 ± 1.0 and 4.9 ± 0.83 ppm respectively for GSP-1 and G-2. They are close to the geometric means⁵⁴. The distribution of pairs of comparison samples between laboratories is thus a useful exercise in a quality assurance programme.

Other methods of identification of biases : The use of reference samples for analytical validation is a very useful approach. However, many such standards are not available. Further, they are expensive and they are to be used with great

discretion. The alternate approaches would be to use the method of standard addition and comparison of data by more than one method which are based on different physicochemical principles.

(i) *Standard addition method :* Many methods of trace element analysis are influenced by matrix. Hence, the preparation of the calibration curves by the addition of different amounts of the analyte to separate aliquots of the same sample, the content of the analyte in the sample being computed from the intercept of the calibration curve. However, this intercept will also include spurious signals which are not corrected for and hence can give positively biased results. Preparation of a matching composition of the sample using pure compounds of the major constituents is not particularly satisfactory for analyses at very low levels of concentration of the analytes since the pure compounds have to be 'free' of the analytes. The standard addition method is useful to correct for low recoveries, particularly when separation steps are involved in the analysis. The isotope dilution method is a special case of standard addition method. Use of radioactive tracers for recovery purposes is a simple approach to correct low recovery⁵⁶. It is, however, necessary to ensure that the spike, active or inactive undergoes complete chemical exchange before the separation step is followed.

(ii) *Comparison with independent method :* The consistency of data obtained by two or more independent methods based on different physicochemical principles gives a guarantee of accuracy of the results, because the biases of different methods are not the same. At the National Bureau of Standards, for a large number of analyses, NAA is considered as a reference method⁵⁷ since this technique depends upon physical principles which are totally different from the other methods of trace analysis. In the application of atomic absorption, the agreement between the results obtained by the direct method, with those obtained after an extraction step is indicative of accuracy. This approach is helpful to identify the matrix effect in the analysis.

(iii) *A case study :* The development of a method for the determination of molybdenum in brine^{58,59} by this author and colleagues had involved the incorporation of some of the concepts described in the paper. The requirement was for the determination of molybdenum down to 5 ng ml⁻¹ in brine and was needed by the chlor-alkali industry. It was felt desirable that the method could be practiced in the control laboratory of the industry. Voltammetry was considered as a satisfactory technique, both from the point of cost and simplicity and viable, provided molybdenum is preconcentrated from 5 ng ml⁻¹ to 1 µg ml⁻¹; for which chelate extraction or coprecipitation on an inorganic substrate was considered. The need for complete destruction of organic material to ensure

that no spurious signal will not vitiate the reduction signal of molybdenum, weighed against the use of chelate extraction and favoured the coprecipitation of molybdenum on to cadmium sulphide. The final procedure was evaluated, for recovery using high specificity activity ^{99}Mo tracer; for measurement accuracy by comparing the results by voltammetry with those by absorption spectrometry; and for 'blank limit' of determination through a least-square fit of a set of standard addition experiments. The 'blank limit' was found to be 2 ng ml^{-1} .

Conclusions and recommendations

Good analytical accuracy is only possible if the measurement process is precise. Analytical imprecision, independent of the method of determination, increases with decrease in the analyte concentration and becomes inacceptably high when the measurements approach the limit of detection of the instrumental methods, IDL. In case a direct technique of measurement is not accessible to the analyst, or the one that is accessible to him is inadequate, either from the point of IDL or selectivity, then additional steps of sample pretreatment, including separations or concentrations, will have to be incorporated into the analytical methodology with two risks, (i) increase in the magnitude of the blank and (ii) introduction of biases.

Blanks: Reproducibility of the process blanks ensures that the blank corrections are dependable. In trace analysis, blanks can, and should, be kept low by the use of (i) closed system sample treatment, (ii) specially purified reagents and (iii) clean laboratory for sample handling. The magnitude and the reproducibility of the blank defines the limit of detection of the methodology (LOD) as defined by the IUPAC; further, results should be reported only if the derived concentrations are above the LOQ, as recommended by the ACS.

Biases: Additional steps of sample pre-treatment, while helpful for the removal of matrix interferences, are sources of introduction of biases by contamination (positive bias) and losses (negative bias). Losses can be studied by the standard addition approach, provided complete chemical exchange between the added analyte and the chemical species of the analyte in the sample is ensured. Absence of contamination can only be checked by the close agreement between the measured value with the recommended value of reference samples, run along with the sample. The non-availability of appropriate reference samples often leads to the use of spiked synthetic samples of matrix similar to the sample. This is satisfactory except when low trace analyses are required. The alternative is to check the results with those obtained by the use of methods based on different physicochemical principles.

The analytical methods so devised should be rugged so that consistent results can be obtained as between different laboratories. Documentation

of such procedures is one of the important aspect of quality assurance programme of analytical chemistry^{9,10}. In spite of having such documentation of rugged methods, it is possible that laboratory has, or can develop biases in regular analyses which can reveal through the exchange of pairs of samples or reference samples as between laboratories. This is required for quality assessment which along with quality control leads to good quality assurance in analytical chemistry.

Acknowledgement

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References

1. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, Green, London, 1958, p. 142.
2. D. G. PETERS, J. H. HAYES and G. M. HIEFVYE, "Chemical Separations and Measurements: Theory and Practice of Analytical Chemistry", W. B. Sanders, 1974.
3. H. A. LAITENEN and W. E. HARRIS, "Chemical Analysis", McGraw Hill, New York, 1975, p. 534.
4. G. H. MORRISON and R. K. SKOGERBOK in "Trace Analysis. Physical Methods", ed. G. H. MORRISON, Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 1.
5. J. P. CALI and W. P. REED in "Accuracy in Trace Analysis: Sampling, Sample Handling, Analysis", NBS Special Publication 422, 1976, Vol. 1, p. 46.
6. M. SANKAR DAS, 1982, unpublished work.
7. F. J. FLANAGAN, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*, 1972, 37, 1189.
8. K. GOVINDARAJU and I. ROELANDTS, *Geostandards Newslett.*, 1977, 1, 163.
9. S. ABBEY, A. H. GILLIESON and G. FERRAULT, "Sy-2, Sy-3 and MRG-1. A Report on the Collaborative Analysis of Three Canadian Rock Samples for Use as Certified Reference Materials", Report No. MRP/MSL 75-132(TR), 1975.
10. R. M. PARR, "Intercomparison of Minor and Trace Elements in IAEA Animal Muscle (H-4); Report No. 2, IAEA/RL/69, 1980.
11. "Elemental Analysis of Biological Materials. Current Problems and Techniques with Special Reference to Trace Elements", International Atomic Energy Agency, Technical Report No. 197, 1980, Appendix III.
12. C. F. HISKEY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 1440.
13. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B*, 1978, 33, 242.
14. *Anal. Chem.*, 1980, 52, 2242.
15. *Anal. Chem.*, 1983, 55, 2210.
16. E. N. JENKINS and A. A. SMALES, *Quart. Rev. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 10, 83.
17. V. P. GUINN in "Trace Characterisation: Chemical and Physical", eds. W. W. MEINKER and B. F. SCRIBNER, National Bureau of Standards, Monograph 100, 1967, p. 337.
18. G. L. YONG and J. D. WINEFORDNER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1983, 55, 712A.
19. W. J. YOU DEN, "The Collaborative Test", in "Precision Measurement and Calibration, Statistical Concepts and Procedures", NBS Special Publication 300, U. S. Dept. of Commerce, 1963, pp. 151-55.
20. R. L. PLACKETT and J. P. BURMAN, *Biometrika*, 1946, 33, 305.
21. R. C. SANKAR and M. SANKAR DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 787.
22. M. SANKAR DAS, 1982, unpublished work.
23. P. TSCHEPEL, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1982, 54, 913.
21. G. V. IYENGAR and B. SANSONI "Sample Preparation of Biological Materials for Trace Element Analysis" in Ref. 11, p. 73.

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25. T. J. MURPHY, "The Role of the Analytical Blank in Accurate Trace Analysis", Ref. 5, Vol. 1, p. 509.
26. E. BERMAN, "The Challenge of Getting the Lead Out", Ref. 5, Vol. 2, p. 715.
27. S. V. BURANGEY, L. R. ZARAFKAR, R. G. DHANESHWAR and M. SANKAR DAS, 1985, unpublished work.
28. *Analyst*, 1965, 90, 515.
29. M. W. ROWE, *Geostandards Newslett.*, 1981, 5, 220.
30. "National Bureau of Standards, NBS Standard Reference Materials Catalogue", NBS Special Publication 260, U. S. Department of Commerce, 1984-85, p. 2.
31. H. B. DESAI, S. R. KAYASTH, C. G. UDAS and M. SANKAR DAS, *Geostandards Newslett.*, 1983, 7, 325.
32. P. B. PAWASKAR, B. S. MANERIKAR and M. SANKAR DAS, *J. Geol. Soc. India*, 1985, 26, 219.
33. W. J. YOUDEN, "Experimental Designs and ASTM Committees", Ref. 19, p. 159 ; *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1959, 51, 79A.
34. M. SANKAR DAS, *Geostandards Newslett.*, 1979, 3, 199.
35. E. S. GLADNEY and C. E. BURNS, *Geostandards Newslett.*, 1983, 7, 3.
36. V. G. PRABHU, L. R. ZARAFKAR and M. SANKAR DAS, *Microchim. Acta*, 1980, 67, II.
37. L. A. CURRIE, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1982, 54, 750.
38. V. G. PRABHU, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1982.
39. J. K. TAYLOR, *Anal. Chem.*, 1981, 53, 1588A.